

IMPACTS OF YAGYA ON AIR QUALITY

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Abstract: The whole world is suffering from pollution and global warming. In India, every year, during the Dussehra and Deepawali occasions, the pollution and haze in India are high due to the burning of firecrackers that cause various health problems to the people of the country. Additionally, due to the lack of scientific information, farmers of Punjab and Haryana burn the agricultural waste of their crops, making the air more polluted and difficult to breathe. Air pollution is not limited to these sources only, there are others factors as well i.e., significant contamination sources, such as factories, thermal power plants, and excessive vehicular use. Particulate Matters (PM) are a by-product of air pollution and a source of health risks. Studies show a substantial link between PM and lung diseases such as cancer, heart disease, neonatal mortality rate, etc. Particles size less than 2.5 μm are classified as a health threat due to their ability to penetrate deep into the lungs. Yagya is a practice referenced in ancient books like the Vedas and Upanishads that is used to purify the environment, particularly filthy air. According to preliminary findings, Yagya reduces SO_2 and NO_2 levels in addition to biological air pollutants like microbes.

Index Terms – air pollution; Yagya; pollution reduction; environment

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution is a major threat to everyone nowadays, especially air pollution. Whether it is ambient air or indoor. Indoor air pollution has a massive impact on humans and it's all due to the usage of advanced technological gadgets. Additionally, there are emerging strains of bacteria and viruses that are drug-resistant and cause new diseases (Saxena et al., 2018). Finding a remedy that might stop or reduce the rising air pollution is urgently needed. However, there is no effective remedy for the radiation and polluting particles in the air. The government is trying to cope with the issue by using different technologies as required as possible. According to a study, the practice known as Yagya, which is referenced in ancient books such as the Vedas and Upanishads, can reduce particulate matter (PM) caused by air pollution, especially in indoor environments (Saxena et al., 2007). Herbs are sacrificed in the fire during a rite called a Yagya as rhythmic mantras are chanted. Yagya is a ritual that has been practiced for centuries to purify the environment. The ingredients used in Yagya play a crucial part, the fragrance of those ingredients and the chanting of mantras spreads in the atmosphere show a tremendous effect on the management of environmental pollution as well as strengthens the religious and psychological values among the society.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

There has been a definite increase in interest in air pollution worldwide during the past few years. Due to increased urbanization and economic expansion, the issue has reached a point where acute as well as chronic effects of air pollution are being noticed (Chen et al., 2012).

Asia is one of the continents with the worst air pollution. Nearly 92 percent of the Asian population, is affected by air pollution. In addition to posing a serious health concern, air pollution from the Asia-Pacific area also harms the environment and crop yields, which has economic repercussions that have an impact on both economic growth and welfare (Clean air Asia, 2017).

As per the report of the World Health Organization (WHO), around seven million individuals worldwide have died as a result of air pollution exposure, which might cause respiratory illnesses, lung cancer, heart diseases, and other medical conditions. More than two-thirds of these deaths have occurred in Asia (WHO, 2015).

PM is a mixture of heterogeneous components that varies substantially by place and season. Organic carbon (OC), elemental carbon (EC), nitrate, sulfate, and trace elements are among their constituents. These chemical substances come from a variety of anthropogenic and natural sources, including sea salt, road dust, biomass gasification, automobile exhaust, and forest fires (Mirowsky et al., 2013).

Acid rain is a type of precipitation with a lower pH than normal that affects plants, and aquatic life, and ruins infrastructure, monuments, and buildings. Nitrogen oxides and airborne sulphur are two variables that contribute to acid rain (Valavanidis et al., 2016).

Chronically exposure to high atmospheric CO_2 levels can have a variety of negative health impacts, including oxidative stress, inflammatory response, altered bone and kidney, respiratory acidosis, and physiological abnormalities (Zappulla et al., 2008).

Vehicles produce carbon monoxide (CO), however light-duty, gasoline-powered vehicles are the main source of CO emissions. One important cause of air pollution in cities is urban road traffic, which has a negative impact on people's health (Mukherjee et al., 2001). Both hypo-toxic and non-hypo-toxic strategies are used by carbon monoxide to affect cell metabolism. Tissue hypoxia has a significant aftereffect of acute carbon monoxide poisoning. The majority of its symptoms include nausea, headache, dizziness, vomiting, blurred vision, chest pain, weakness, as well as cardiac arrest, coma, respiratory arrest, hypotension, and pulmonary edema (Kao et al., 2006).

Ozone at ground level has an immediate negative impact on the respiratory and cardiovascular systems. Long-term exposure results in respiratory mortality, childhood asthma, and asthmatic symptoms in people (Nuvolone et al. 2018). The high concentration of NO_x enters the atmosphere through natural processes. It contributes to the development of photochemical smog, which has a profound impact on people's wellness. Wheezing, colds, coughing, and bronchitis are a few consequences that might result from a high concentration of NO_x (Dohmen et al., 1984).

Since sulfur dioxide is an unstable chemical, it readily reacts with water to produce sulphuric acid. Oxides of sulfur are produced during the burning of fossil fuels that include sulfur. According to Schlesinger et al., SO₂ is the most prevalent gas among all sulfur oxides and is extremely toxic to all living things, including plants and animals.

The study on Yagya draws on historical, philosophical, and contemporary research. We can understand its importance considering the state of the planet, which is affected by environmental issues (Kumar, 2019).

A study by Rathi, 2019, shows that when the Yagya is performed consistently, it creates a pure, nourishing, therapeutic and pleasant atmosphere in our surroundings and lowers the likelihood of diseases. It regenerates brain cells, rejuvenates the skin, cleanses the blood, and inhibits the development of pathogenic organisms. When cow ghee is used in a Yagya, the smoke it produces greatly reduces the impact of atomic radiation on the area. Yagya ash purifies the water, making it suitable for consumption.

The policymakers to design a policy that prioritizes reducing air pollution over mitigating climate change and vice versa are examined in detail. There is evidence that models with a focus on climate change and end-of-pipe air pollution measures are more economical and result in greater social benefits (Wagner et al., 2014).

III. MATERIAL & METHODS

The study was conducted to verify the effect of Yagya on reducing the environmental pollution. The environmental condition was continuously monitored commencing eight hours prior to the beginning of Yagya, during the Yagya and after the completion of Yagya. The havan samagri was pre-soaked in ghee, which caused it to burn quickly and fully and produce the least amount of PM.

3.1 Effects on the following parameters were analyzed:

AAQM Particulate Parameters

- PM 10 (Particulate Matter of size ≤ 10 micron)
- PM 2.5 (Particulate Matter of size ≤ 2.5 micron)

AAQM Gaseous Parameters

- CO₂ (Carbon Dioxide)
- CO (Carbon Monoxide)
- O₂ (Oxygen)
- SO₂ (Sulphur Dioxide)
- NO_x (Oxides of Nitrogen)
- O₃ (Ozone)
- NH₃ (Ammonia)

The study was conducted in two sessions, each session divided into three phases i.e., Pre Yagya, During Yagya, and Post Yagya. Details of which have been discussed below in the table:

Table 3.1: Shows the monitoring time and dates of air sampling

Sessions	Phases	Date and Timings
Session I	Pre Yagya	25 October 2021 (9:25 AM-5:25 PM)
	During Yagya	26 October 2021 (7:00 AM-6:30 PM)
	Post Yagya	26 October 2021 - 27 October 2021 (6:30 PM-6:30 AM)
Session II	Pre Yagya	26 October 2021 - 27 October 2021 (6:30 PM-6:30 AM)
	During Yagya	27 October 2021 (7:15 AM-7:15 PM)
	Post Yagya	27 October 2021 - 28 October 2021 (7:30 PM-7:30 AM)

Sampling and analysis were carried out in accordance with the steps outlined by Indian Standards. The sample and analysis techniques used have been described below, parameter by parameter:

Table 3.2: Shows the Test parameter, methods used and the instructions

Test Parameter	Test Method	Instructions/Procedures
PM 10	IS 5182 (Part-23)	The sampling procedure involved the use of a respirable dust sampler. Each set of samples was sampled for 8 hours at a vacuum pressure of 1.1 m ³ /min, and the sample was taken using a glass microfiber filter paper.
PM 2.5	IS 5182 (Part-24)	The sampling procedure involved the use of a PM 2.5 sampler. Each set of samples was sampled for 8 hours at a vacuum pressure of 16.7 lpm, with the sample being collected on PTFE filter paper.
SO ₂	IS 5182 (Part-2)	For the purpose of sampling, a respirable dust sampler and a gaseous attachment both were utilized. A suitable volume of the proper absorbing solutions was placed in the impingers, and the air was forced through them at a rate of 1 lpm. With the exception of ozone, which was sampled for only an hour, the sampling period was 8 hours.
NO _x	IS 5182 (Part-6)	
NH ₃	APHA-Air 3 rd edition, 1989, Method No. 401	
O ₃	IS 5182 (Part-9)	
CO ₂	-	The value of these parameters was analyzed by using the respective meters on an hourly basis.
CO	-	
O ₂	-	

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

The study was quite extensive, and the session-by-session parameter data and graphical comparison are shown below:

- Air monitoring results of PM 10 and PM 2.5

Table 4.1: Shows PM 10 and PM 2.5 results during monitoring of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

Sessions	Phases	PM 10 (µg/m ³)	PM 2.5 (µg/m ³)
Session 1	Pre Yagya	561.30	141.25
	During Yagya	403.55	124.10
	Post Yagya	282.00	81.20
Session 2	Pre Yagya	282.00	81.20
	During Yagya	355.35	110.42
	Post Yagya	279.42	79.25

Figure 1: shows a graphical representation of PM 10 results of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

Figure 2: shows a graphical representation of PM 2.5 results of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

- Air Monitoring results of Sulphur dioxide (SO₂), Oxides of Nitrogen (NO_x), Ozone (O₃), Ammonia (NH₃):

Table 4.2: shows the results of SO₂, NO_x, O₃ and NH₃ of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

	Phases	SO ₂ (µg/m ³)	NO _x (µg/m ³)	O ₃ (µg/m ³)	NH ₃ (µg/m ³)
Session 1	Pre Yagya	7.35	34.50	1.02	17.25
	During Yagya	9.80	27.45	2.35	18.60
	Post Yagya	5.32	20.75	0.92	15.10
Session 2	Pre Yagya	5.32	20.75	0.92	15.10
	During Yagya	8.20	25.10	1.85	19.34
	Post-Yagya	4.35	19.42	1.01	13.82

Figure 3: shows a graphical representation of SO₂ results of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

Figure 4: shows a graphical representation of NO_x results of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

Figure 5: shows a graphical representation of O₃ results of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

Figure 6: shows a graphical representation of NH₃ results of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

- Air monitoring results of Carbon Dioxide (CO₂)

Table 4.3: shows the results of carbon dioxide (CO₂) of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

CO ₂ (ppm)					
Session 1			Session 2		
Pre Yagya	During Yagya	Post Yagya	Pre Yagya	During Yagya	Post Yagya
437	515	292	292	287	295
592	418	285	285	309	306
536	332	277	277	301	310
512	305	273	273	295	319
508	286	325	325	282	344
423	259	338	338	278	337
418	271	342	342	265	352
421	287	391	391	277	359

Figure 7: shows a graphical representation of CO₂ results of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

- Air monitoring results of Carbon Monoxide (CO)

Table 4.4: shows the results of carbon monoxide (CO) of pre-Yagya, during Yagya and post-Yagya

CO (ppm)					
Session 1			Session 2		
Pre Yagya	During Yagya	Post Yagya	Pre Yagya	During Yagya	Post Yagya
3	3	0	0	0	0
8	3	1	1	0	0
5	2	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0
3	1	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	1	1	0	0

Figure 8: shows a graphical representation of CO results of pre, during and post-Yagya

• Air monitoring results of Oxygen (O₂)

Table 4.5: shows the results of oxygen (O₂) of pre, during and post-Yagya

O ₂ (%)					
Session 1			Session 2		
Pre Yagya	During Yagya	Post Yagya	Pre Yagya	During Yagya	Post Yagya
19.2	18.7	18.6	18.6	18.8	19.0
18.9	19.1	18.6	18.6	18.8	18.9
18.9	19.1	18.5	18.5	18.6	18.7
18.7	18.5	18.3	18.3	18.5	18.5
18.8	18.7	18.3	18.3	18.6	18.7
18.8	18.3	18.2	18.2	18.4	18.8
18.9	18.5	18.4	18.4	18.9	19.0
19	18.4	18.3	18.3	18.7	18.9

Figure 9: shows a graphical representation of O₂ results of pre, during and post-Yagya

V. Conclusion

The air monitoring was done in two sessions, each of which had three phases: prior to the beginning of Yagya, during the Yagya, and after the Yagya. The study was quite extensive because it took into account a variety of factors, including particulate matter 10 and 2.5, SO₂, NO_x, O₃, NH₃, CO₂ and O₂. According to the study, the values of PM 10, PM 2.5, CO₂ and CO have decreased. Almost constant levels of oxygen were maintained during both periods with few changes. Throughout the time, the levels of other gaseous characteristics fluctuated. One theory for the decrease in PM and CO₂ after the Yagya is that the ghee used in the oblation of the herbs may have volatilized into very small droplets, and particulate matter may have adhered to their surfaces. Therefore, it can result in a decrease in particular pollutants concentration in the atmosphere. The overall study finds that Yagya has a beneficial impact on environmental conditions, with a noticeable decrease in key parameters.

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